

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

HYDROGEN TECHNOLOGY IN AVIATION, WORLDWIDE PERSPECTIVE AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to provide a general perspective on the use of hydrogen technology, which is becoming increasingly widespread in the world, in aviation and to reveal the possible usage predictions within the framework of Turkey's hydrogen vision.

In the study, carbon reduction technologies in the field of aviation are examined, focused on liquid hydrogen technology and its potential areas and technological limitations for usage in civil aviation and finally worldwide activities and planned strategic steps are mentioned.

As a result, despite the current technological limitations, it is evaluated that the 2053 carbon reduction targets will be effective in achieving the targets in the aviation sector in the light of developments in hydrogen technology, with road maps and infrastructure installations determined in line with technological developments.

Keywords: hydrogen technology, aviation, fuel cells, hydrogen fuel, hydrogen combustion.

Introduction

Fossil-based fuels are widely used in aviation due to their high energy density, easy storage option and safe transport characteristics. However, climate change and political tensions with oil producing countries have brought the search for alternative fuels to the agenda in the aviation sector [1].

According to measurements in 2018, 2.56% of greenhouse gas emissions generated by the civil aviation sector (1.1 Gt CO₂). Between 2005 and 2019, despite technological advances in the aviation sector, CO₂ levels increased by 42%, and are estimated to double by 2050. A zero carbon footprint target has been set for the aviation sector to reduce emissions by 2050 [2].

ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization) has long term plans to reduce CO₂ emissions in aviation operations, aircraft and fuel technologies. For this reason, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), ICAO, International Air Transport Association (IATA) have formed a coalition to work on decarbonization, CO₂ and other emissions and their environmental impacts on the environment. The coalition includes 47 partners committed to sustainable aviation and the transformation of the industry. The ICAO global coalition includes companies such as Airbus and Archer, as well as Cranfield and Eindhoven Universities [3].

In the aviation industry, kerosene or naphtha type fuels called jet fuels that produced from petroleum are used. Kerosene fuels are sorted as Jet A, Jet A-1, JP 5 and JP 8 fuels with carbon numbers between 8-16. Naphtha-type fuels are Jet B and JP-4 fuels with a wide carbon range of 5-15. These fuels are also used as kerosene-naphtha and kerosene-gasoline (JP-4) blends [4].

These fuels must be selected in accordance with the intended use of the aircraft and must meet the required standards. It was reported by Yilmaz et al. that in terms of flight safety, it is important to know the important properties of the fuels to be used in commercial flights such as octane number, flash point and freezing point in order to select the right fuel according to the region where it will be used, and on the other hand, JP

fuels used for military purposes must also meet NATO standards. It is stated that synthetic fuels and blends can also be used to meet the properties of these fuels produced from petroleum due to the increasing need for fuel, and in this context, alternative fuels to be used in aircraft must meet sustainable/renewable aviation fuel standards such as European renewable energy directive (EU-RED), US renewable fuel standards (US-RFS2) or RSB [5].

In the European Commission's clean aviation perspective, a few key ideas arise from the cooperation: To reduce emissions by 30% by 2030 and to establish an innovation-based, reliable, safe and cost-effective European aviation system to achieve the climate change target by 2050 by launching new products by 2035 as a result of increasing technological and industrial maturity [6]. According to the report published by IATA in 2020, it is predicted that the use of the following technologies instead of petroleum-type fuels will reduce the impact of climate change. These new technologies and fuel perspectives are estimated to contribute to achieving the long-term overall industry goal for reducing aviation's global carbon footprint by 50 percent by 2050 (compared to 2005 levels) [7].

- a) Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs):
 - Biofuels (hydro-processed esters and saturated oils, biomass)
 - E-kerosene, e-fuels- low carbon or carbon-free fuels produced by the Fischer-Tropsch process using hydrogen and CO₂ from industrial processes
- b) Hydrogen-based fuels
- c) New propulsion technologies
 - Battery-electric, hybrid-electric Technologies
 - Use of hydrogen as fuel in combustion engines
- d) An all-electric aircraft based on electricity generated from a carbon-free source (which can completely eliminate CO₂ emissions in its operation).

Biofuels and synthetic fuels do not cause changes in the existing aviation fuel infrastructure and have no limits in terms of range (from 19-seater aircraft to long-

range 250 seater aircraft). As an advantage, battery-electric technologies have no impact on climate change, while hydrogen technologies are reported to have a high potential climate change reduction impact. However, these new technologies have range limits. For example, medium-long range application is not practical with battery-electric technology, whereas for hydrogen, advanced design solutions are needed for long range [7].

Although SAFS generates the same amount of CO₂ as jet fuel when burned, it has been presented as a solution to carbon reduction since it leads to 70 to 100% emission reduction in the production process and product life cycle compared to jet fuels [9], but its use in airports requires changes in infrastructure and new approaches are needed [8].

There are increasing studies that hydrogen will replace petroleum-based fuels and will be much more advantageous than petroleum-based fuels both economically and environmentally [9]. When used as a fuel in a jet engine, it emits only water vapor and prevents carbon-based emissions such as sulfur and nitrogen oxides [10].

The European Union, in its EU hydrogen strategy, has declared that hydrogen is vital to achieving the 2050 climate change targets. The policy aims to ensure that hydrogen production is mainly from renewable energy sources (green hydrogen), that solar energy and wind energy will take the place of fossil fuels (gray hydrogen) and that the use of hydrogen will increase [11].

Background of Hydrogen Technology

While hydrogen is not a natural fuel source, it can be produced from sources such as water, biomass, nuclear and hydrocarbons utilizing primary energy production and stored as an energy carrier, which can then be used in a fuel cell to generate electricity and heat. Hydrogen is a clean fuel that produces only water, electricity and heat when consumed in a fuel cell. Hydrogen and fuel cells have an important role in the field of energy production with the potential to be used in a wide range of applications in almost all sectors, especially transportation, industry and housing. Hydrogen is produced by steam reforming of methane in a high-temperature process [12]. Although this method produces 90% of the hydrogen produced in the world, it is the method that produces the most greenhouse gases [13]. Hydrogen can also be produced through biochemical reactions using microorganisms such as bacteria or microalgae [12].

Several studies have been conducted to explore the production of hydrogen by hydrolysis process from metal hydrides and high H-containing compounds (ammonia borane, hydrazine, etc.) and the research process is still underway. Hydrogen production by means of hydrolysis is possible in solid or solution form of these compounds. In particular, metal hydrides are preferred, since the production of hydrogen from alkaline water solutions of metal hydrides redoubled the amount of hydrogen produced, and the alkaline medium NaBH₄, LiBH₄, KBH₄ remains stable, can be stored for a long time [14].

Types of Hydrogen:

Hydrogen can be produced through a variety of processes, all of which have a different climate impact. In order to enhance clarity, this paper will use the following definitions:

Green hydrogen: hydrogen produced through the electrolysis of water, with electricity from renewable sources; greenhouse gas emissions close to zero.

Yellow hydrogen: hydrogen produced through the electrolysis of water, using nuclear electricity; greenhouse gas emissions close to zero.

Blue hydrogen: hydrogen produced through steam methane reforming with carbon capture and storage (CCS); low levels of greenhouse gas emissions.

Turquoise hydrogen: hydrogen produced through pyrolysis with carbon black as a by-product; low levels of greenhouse gas emissions

Grey hydrogen: hydrogen produced through steam methane reforming without CCS, using natural gas; high levels of greenhouse gas emissions.

Renewable hydrogen: synonym for green hydrogen

Clean hydrogen: synonym for green hydrogen

Low-carbon hydrogen: encompasses fossil-based hydrogen with carbon capture and electricity-based hydrogen, with significantly reduced full life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions compared to existing hydrogen production; it includes green, yellow, blue, and turquoise hydrogen.

Figure 1 Hydrogen Energy Colors According to Hydrogen Production Methods [15]

Hydrogen, when produced by electrolysis, does not cause CO₂ emissions and thus can be used directly as a sustainable aviation fuel in air transport or in the production of hydrogen vehicles (on-board) to meet the goal of decarbonization [16].

In studies for the use of hydrogen in aviation, it will result in refueling speeds comparable to fossil fuels, lower noise for engine operation, and lower carbon emissions. For example, studies by the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) have shown that hydrogen refueling speeds in vehicles are comparable to Jet A. In 2022, NREL achieved an average fill rate of 14 kg/min (21 kg/min maximum flow) in heavy tonnage vehicles [16].

The cost of hydrogen is high compared to other sustainable energy sources. To address this, in 2021, the US Department of Energy (DOE) has set a target of \$1 for 1 kg of hydrogen within 10 years, which it defines as "1 1 1". Another bottleneck is the emissions from the production of hydrogen from non-fossil sources. The most economical and conventional production method is steam reforming of methane, and to be a major player in aviation, it must be produced by cost-effective methods in terms of electrolyzers or carbon capture technologies [17].

Hydrogen Storage Technologies

There are many ways to store hydrogen for later use. From the thermodynamic point of view, it has hydrogen boils at $-252.77\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (20.33 K), the melting point is at $259.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the critical point is at $-240\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 1 atm. The density is 0.0899 g/l at standard atmosphere. Liquid hydrogen has a specific gravity of 70.99 g/l, which is 790 times the one of gaseous hydrogen. The volume-related energy density of liquid hydrogen is about 1/4 that of gasoline and about 1/3 that of natural gas. The weight content of hydrogen in water is 11.2% [18].

When the technologies for the use of hydrogen in aviation are examined, gaseous hydrogen in pressurized form, compressed gaseous hydrogen, cryogenic compressed hydrogen, cryogenic liquid hydrogen, metal hybrid hydrogen storage, chemical hydrogen storage, organic hydrogen storage and adsorption hydrogen storage are shown as alternatives. However, having aviation in Hydrogen Storage Technology for Aerial Vehicles in mind, because of the additional safety risks going along with the regeneration of hydrogen, today only the physical storage of hydrogen in a vessel is in the focus of the development in the aviation industry [18].

There are four main physical storage conditions which are used today for hydrogen in a tank. Typically compressed hydrogen CH₂ is used at 700 and 350 bar.

It has to be noted that the stored density rises with increasing pressure and decreasing temperature. The highest density changes occur near the critical point (CP). Therefore, the use of liquid hydrogen (LH₂) and cryogenic compressed hydrogen (CryoCH₂) are of high interest for the aviation industry.

Also, usage of liquid hydrogen in place of kerosene as a sustainable aviation fuel is investigated in terms of performance and environmental aspects and is evaluated as is currently the most suitable technology, based on technological maturity [19].

The liquefied hydrogen storage tank developed by MAGNA STEYR Fahrzeugtechnik AG & Co KG is shown in Figure 2. This tank, consisting of an inner and an outer tank, stores approximately 10 kg of hydrogen. The materials used to make this tank are stainless steel or aluminium alloy. Both materials are very resistant to hydrogen embrittlement and exhibit negligible hydrogen permeation. In addition, their low specific weight, high strength, and high coefficient of thermal expansion, combined with excellent thermal conductivity properties, make the total weight of the tank with accessories around 150 kg [20].

Figure 2 Liquefied hydrogen storage tank [20]

Hydrogen tanks can be classified into five types according to the structure of the materials used [21].

Table 1

Classification and applications of different hydrogen tanks.

Type	Schematic	Materials			Maximum pressure (bar)	Applications
		Metal	Composite	Polymer		
I		Steel/Al	/	/	Al: 175 Steel: 200	Submarine applications
II		Steel/Al liner	Filament windings around the cylinder part	/	Al/glass: 263 Steel/carbon fibre: 299	Stationary fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) technologies
III		Al/Steel liner	Composite over-wrap (fibre glass/aramid or carbon fibre)	/	Al/glass: 305 Al/aramid: 438 Al/carbon: 700	Vehicles
IV		/	Composite over-wrap (carbon fibre)	Polymer liner	350 (buses) 700	Vehicles
V		/	Composite	/	1000	Aerospace applications

Type I hydrogen tanks are made of metal only [21]. Common metals used include steel and aluminium alloy, easy to manufacture among the five types and thus, the cheapest. They can be made to have a huge capacity mainly used for either stationary applications such as the large-scale storage of industrial hydrogen or large vessels such as submarines [23]. Type II hydrogen tanks are also all-metal cylinders which are similar to Type I except that they have carbon fibre or glass fibre filament wrapped around their straight body part [21].

Type III and Type IV hydrogen tanks are solutions for automobile applications due to significant weight savings as compared to Type I and Type II [20]. Both types are fully wrapped with composite, normally carbon fibre T700S or T800S. The only difference is that Type III uses metallic liner while Type IV uses polymeric liner. For Type III tanks, the metals used for the liner is commonly AA6061 or AA7000 as these alloy species have a good machineability and can be heat treated to gain better mechanical properties. Due to the high strength (4900 MPa) and low density (1.80 g/cm^3) of T700S carbon fibre, both Type III and Type IV tanks allow higher internal pressures as compared to other types and the overall tank weight and wall thickness are significantly lower [23].

Type V hydrogen tanks are fully composite. It is about 20% lighter than Type IV tanks and can withstand an even higher pressure of about 1000 bar [22]. However, this technology is still in development and

the current high cost of composite materials restricts its applications commercially [21].

Here, drawbacks for liquid hydrogen-powered aircraft are mentioned [24]:

Optimal layout: liquid hydrogen requires 4 times more volume than kerosene, and the large volume leads to modifications in the aircraft design, reducing the available space required for aerodynamic efficiency and payload. To store hydrogen in liquid form, spherical or cylindrical tanks are required to keep the temperature low, prevent hydrogen evaporation and minimize losses. **Insulation:** Appropriate insulation is required to minimize heat transfer from the tank and to keep the internal temperature and pressure at appropriate levels [24].

There is a possibility of catastrophic accident risk such as explosion and fire as a result of exothermic reaction when in contact with oxygen during depressurization of the tank that may occur when there is a structural problem. In addition, due to the materials in the structure of the hydrogen tank, the strength of the material decreases when exposed to liquid hydrogen for a long time [25].

Center of gravity position: While modern aircraft carry most of their fuel on the wings, the concept of using hydrogen tanks requires positioning the tank along the horizontal axis. Therefore, the placement of the liquid hydrogen tank is seen as a crucial step in the commercialization of the technology. [24], [26], [27].

Figure 3 Conventional storage view (a) view of kerosene tank on wings (b) proposed layout solution for short, medium range aircraft (c) proposed layout solution for long range aircraft [28]

While kerosene tanks are generally suitable for wing placement, liquid hydrogen tanks are not suitable for wing transportation due to the volume requirements. Liquid hydrogen has a lower density in volume than kerosene, but needs sufficient space when stored in tanks and needs insulation. Thus, possible deployment scenarios for liquid hydrogen transportation have been developed. For short-medium range flights, behind the cabin and above the cabin are envisaged, while for long range flights, behind the cockpit and behind the cabin are recommended [28].

Future Hydrogen Solutions for Aviation

To reach the goal of decarbonization in aviation, a holistic approach is needed, including improvement of existing technologies, establishing novel energy system approaches, as well as consulting of aircraft certification and training standards. The new energy technologies will come in the form of high-efficiency engines, power system components and high-energy batteries,

liquid/gas fuel tanks, advanced material composites and power electronics, depending on the fuels to be used as an alternative to the existing system. Such technologies will also lead to design improvements in ground support equipment, such as induction charging, and high energy support for long-range aircraft during parking.

The main technologies that stand out for decarbonization are summarized below:

In the hybrid electric aircraft concept, the electric motor and turbofan are configured in series or in parallel, and power is supplied from the battery. When high power is required, the electric motor works with the turbofan, while only the electric motor operates at low power or cruise [29]. Despite its advantages in terms of fuel savings, emission reduction and noise reduction, battery technology has technological limitations due to its low energy density of 0.2-0.5 kWh/kg and limited

lifetime. While the battery is operated for initial powering, the fuel cell is used as additional power for cruise, climbing and take-off [30]. Fuel cells can be used with either conventional combustion (turbo electric) technologies. Battery-electric propulsion is considered to be the best option for flight with no emissions or emission-based impacts [31]. Electric propulsion is seen as an alternative for sustainable aviation for journeys under 500 miles.

Low noise and emissions, low maintainability, low operating costs and the use of technologies based on existing infrastructure (although improvements are also needed) are important advantages of this technology.

Electric vertical take-off and landing (eVOL), alternative propulsion techniques and short-range aircraft are of interest to many companies. Some manufacturers are negotiating with the American Aviation Authority (FAA) for certification processes, while others are developing innovative propulsion systems through col-

laborations, conducting test flights and following International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) approved processes [17].

Two main technologies stand out in the use of hydrogen as a fuel in the aviation industry. The first is the use of hydrogen with a fuel cell in the small aircraft category. Trials are being conducted for aircraft in this category, and it seems likely that it will be on the market in the coming years with studies performed in parallel with existing examples, depending on hydrogen limitations and boundary conditions. The second category is the large commercial aircraft category; the use of hydrogen in gas turbines requires further work to develop this technology [32].

Hydrogen can be used as fuel in a hydrogen-powered engine by hydrogen combustion or as fuel cells to power electric motors. If it is used in the engine to substitute jet fuel, it will require modifications to the combustor design and flame stability. In addition, nitrogen dioxide and its derivatives are still released as emissions in combustion [33].

Figure 4 Hydrogen Propulsion System [34]

The Figure 4 shows two combustion systems that arise in the use of hydrogen. In hydrogen combustion method, thrust is generated through the combustion of hydrogen in a modified jet engine. This process eliminates the CO_2 , CO , SO_x and the majority of soot emissions generated by conventional jet engines. NO_x and water vapor are still emitted, representing some contribution to atmospheric GHG levels. Fuel cell aircraft could potentially offer a "true zero" solution for GHG emissions. The only output of fuel cells is water, which eliminates CO_2 , NO_x , SO_x , CO , HC and soot emissions. However, the water produced – around nine kilograms for every one kilogram of hydrogen reacted – would have to be released, and water vapor is also a GHG [34].

In both of these systems, it is proposed to use liquid hydrogen as hydrogen [20,34,36,37].

Hydrogen Applications in Aviation

The origins of hydrogen studies in aviation date back to the 1937s. The German jet engine prototype

Heinkel HeS-1 was powered purely by hydrogen [38]. In 1956, the NACA B-57 was modified to run on LH_2 and liquid hydrogen was converted to gas through a heat exchanger and fed to the burner. Two liquid hydrogen (LH_2) tanks were placed in the wings and powered for 20 minutes before takeoff. [39]. The Russians have also been involved in liquid hydrogen studies. In 1988, the Russian aircraft manufacturer Tupolev proved that liquid hydrogen could be used as an alternative fuel with modifications to a Tu-154 (renamed Tu-155) [39].

"Cryoplane", a 36-partner project carried out by the EU in 2000, involving parties such as industry and research institutions, aims to realize the concept design of hydrogen-fueled turbomotor technology and liquid hydrogen storage technology [26]. As a result of its know-how and technological collaborations, Airbus launched the ZEROe project, aiming to realize the world's first zero-emission commercial aircraft with a capacity of 100 seats by 2035. In 2022, the hydrogen

tank, hydrogen combustion engine and liquid hydrogen delivery system were started to be tested on the ground on the A380 model test aircraft as part of the demonstrator aircraft, and the entire system was planned to be verified in flight. The first flight is expected to be performed within the next 5 years. Another step of the project is the development of a hydrogen combustion engine (GE and SAFRAN). 2019 yılında Alman hükümeti “Geleceğin Havacılığı için Leipzig Beyanı” ile gürültü kirliliği önleyecek verimlilik arttıracak hidrojen altyapısı kurma stratejisini yayınlamıştır [40].

Rolls-Royce and Easyjet set out to prove that hydrogen can safely and efficiently generate power for civil aviation engines. The hydrogen utilized to power the jet engine in the concept is reportedly sourced from tidal and wind energy in Scotland's Orkney Islands. According to the companies, the new product is an important step towards proving that hydrogen can be the zero-carbon aviation fuel of the future, and the new engine is seen as an important milestone in the decarbonization strategies of Rolls-Royce and easyJet, which are taking a green approach. The test was conducted at an open-air test facility at MoD Boscombe Down, UK, using a converted Rolls-Royce AE 2100-A regional aircraft engine, and following analysis of the initial concept ground test, the partnership is planning a series of further equipment tests leading up to a full-scale ground test of the Rolls-Royce Pearl 15 jet engine.

The Boston Consulting Group (BCG) has joined with Air Canada, Air France-KLM, American Airlines, JetBlue, Luft-hansa, Cathay Pacific, Delta Air Lines, Southwest Airlines, United Airlines and Virgin Atlantic to form the Aviation Climate Taskforce (ACT), a new organization to support sustainable travel. Their goal is to work on a non-profit basis to support sustainable technologies that reduce carbon emissions and promote sustainable energy through bio-based Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) and hydrogen solutions.

ZeroAvia, Royal Schiphol Group, Rotterdam The Hague Innovation Airport Foundation and Rotterdam the Hague Airport (RTHA) have partnered to realize the first zero-emission 70-seat commercial passenger flights between the UK and the Netherlands, with plans to fly the first 19-seat hydrogen-powered aircraft between Rotterdam The Hague Airport and London in 2025. Their aim is to facilitate the commercial adoption of hydrogen-electric aviation[41].

H2FLY, the Stuttgart, Germany-based developer of hydrogen-electric powertrain systems for aircraft, first piloted flight of an electric aircraft powered by liquid hydrogen. The H2FLY team has completed four flights powered by liquid hydrogen as part of its flight test campaign, including one flight that lasted for over three hours. The flights were completed with H2FLY's piloted HY4 demonstrator aircraft, fitted with a hydrogen-electric fuel cell propulsion system and cryogenically stored liquid hydrogen that powered the aircraft. Results of the test flights indicate that using liquid hydrogen in place of gaseous hydrogen will double the maximum range of the HY4 aircraft from 750 km to 1,500 km, marking a critical step towards the delivery of emissions-free, medium- and long-haul commercial flights [42].

Conclusion

A closer look at studies around the world reveals that there is an increasing demand for hydrogen. An overview of the existing technological infrastructures shows that the use of hydrogen as a fuel will be possible in the long term and will lead to changes in aircraft design and fuel distribution and storage infrastructure.

From an EU perspective, when current technologies are analyzed, it is reported that while biofuels and turbo-electric aircraft offer a short-term solution for reducing carbon in aviation, in the long term, battery-electric, hydrogen-powered aircraft solutions should be evaluated for long-range flights [41].

For utilization as a fuel, there is a necessity to establish infrastructures targeting green hydrogen capable of producing at larger capacities, and to achieve technological maturity in hydrogen logistics, including hydrogen distribution, storage and liquefaction capacity. In the concept of utilization at airports, refueling and on-site storage, the need for the installation of infrastructure suitable for new aircraft concepts, the development of the safety framework (leakage, fire, transportation of liquid hydrogen) and the establishment of regulations; in the hydrogen aircraft concept, the design of the hydrogen aircraft should be made to carry liquid hydrogen, the propulsion system should be highly efficient, and a safe and reliable fuel distribution system should be installed [42].

Additional security requirements should be met in terms of safety due to the explosive and flammable properties of hydrogen. It is also emphasized that for safety, certification and compliance demonstration methods for hydrogen technologies have to be determined and regulations and standards have to be established.

Aviation authorities such as ICAO and FAA consider that the targeted steps will be realized through international cooperation, agreements and policies targeting the reduction of carbon emissions at every stage from the use of fuel in aviation to aircraft technology. They also state that the use of hydrogen in gas turbines or through fuel cells will enable cleaner combustion compared to liquid fuels, that the absence of carbon-based emissions and very low nitrogen oxides will improve air quality and that aviation fuels are important in mitigating climate impacts.

The international community has made progress in developing standards for hydrogen emissions, safety and operations. While ISO and UNIDO are joining forces to develop international standards in the field of systems and devices for the production, storage, transport, measurement and use of hydrogen, there is still plenty of work that needs to be done to finalize the standards, especially in the areas of safety, operations and [44]. Developing countries must actively engage in this process to ensure they can benefit from the global H₂ market. These benefits include access to the global GH₂ market, attracting investments and partnerships by demonstrating that they are “hydrogen-ready”, facilitating technology transfer, building technical capacity, reducing trade barriers, and shaping the development of standards to align with their unique needs.

Current studies indicate that fuel cells will be used in small regional aircraft or business jets, while hydrogen combustion engines will be actively used in small and medium-sized aviation applications towards the 2030s. The EU roadmap aims to focus on the two-phase approach to develop fuel cell-based regional aircraft (50-100 passengers, <1000nm) and propulsion systems in which hydrogen is directly combusted, with short-medium range aircraft concepts (<200 passengers, <2000nm) coming to the fore. In the first phase (2022-2025), the main focus is on technology maturation (hydrogen storage, MW-level fuel cell systems, etc.) and the development of hydrogen combustion aircraft configurations. In the second phase (2025-2030), technology developers will frozen the development and perform integration and demonstration activities until 2029 [45].

In the vision of Turkey's hydrogen vision published in the Turkey Hydrogen Technologies Strategy and Roadmap, hydrogen has been declared as one of the high prioritized areas due to its impact on the sustainable energy future. In line with the economic development and 2053 net zero carbon emission targets, it is aimed to create a carbon zero economy model by using hydrogen and the importance of developing domestic technologies in the fields of production, storage and distribution of hydrogen has been emphasized.

Since it is considered that Turkey has the potential to produce hydrogen and to be a technology developer in the short, medium and long term. Hence, it is assessed that the hydrogen produced through R&D activities can be utilized both domestically and exported abroad. It is important to establish an infrastructure from the production of hydrogen to its transmission and end-user by 2053 in order to meet carbon footprint targets, which have become widespread in different sectors.

In the development of a national hydrogen strategy for Turkey; understanding the opportunities offered by green hydrogen to reduce dependence on energy imports, funding renewable energy investments, planning renewable energy integration for green hydrogen production, quantifying the costs, social, economic and environmental benefits of hydrogen production, creating a domestic hydrogen ecosystem, and determining the role of green hydrogen in Turkey's energy transition strategy are shown as priority areas for the realization of it [46].

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